

Assessment of particularization of orthodontic posts related to temporary anchorage devices on Instagram

Dr. Bharvi Jani^{1*}, Dr. Falguni Mehta², Dr. Alap Shah³, Dr. Dhanvi Desai⁴, Dr Ridhima Gaunkar⁵,
Dr Setu Patel⁶

1. *Ph.D. Scholar (Gujarat University), Associate Professor,
Department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics
Karnavati school of dentistry*
2. *Ph.D. Guide (Gujarat University), Professor and Head,
Department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics,
Government dental college and hospital*
3. *Professor and Head,
Department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics
Karnavati school of dentistry*
4. *Post graduate student,
Department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics
Karnavati school of dentistry*
5. *Professor
Department of Public Health Dentistry
Goa Dental College and Hospital*
6. *PhD Scholar (Gujarat University)
Assistant Professor,
College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre.*

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Abstract

Objectives: To investigate content of temporary anchorage devices-related posts on Instagram for the assessment of completeness of information available.

Materials and Methods: Three 'hashtags' related to Temporary Anchorage Devices (TADS) were determined, and posts with #tads were included in the final dataset of instagram. A total of 3,348 posts were screened, and 88 were included in the study. The posts were further divided based on the biomechanics.

Results: Out of the total posts included (n=88), a greater number of posts depicting intrusion mechanics (56.59%) and cant correction (19.32%) were found.

Conclusion: It was noted that amongst the recently available information related to TADs only 2.6% was complete. Thus, the need for awareness regarding complete information sharing is inevitable.

Key words: *Temporary anchorage device, TADS, social media, Instagram, mini-implants, miniscrews*

INTRODUCTION

Social media is becoming an integral tool for information sharing in these transforming times. Communication via visuals, text and videos can be done across any part of the world at just a click [1,2]. In recent times, use of social media has not only improved the way we present information but has also provided a platform for individuals to showcase their creative and intellectual skills [3].

More than 3.9 billion (51.2 %) world's population uses internet. 'Blogging' has nowadays become a trending way of communication on networking websites [4]. With more than one billion members, Instagram has become even more popular [5].

Social media has a significant impact on healthcare, as a tool to create awareness and educate patients/fellow colleagues [6]. In recent times, dentistry has undergone a transformation by embracing social media as a potent tool for efficient marketing and communication. This trend is mirrored in the field of orthodontics, where social media has become an equally effective platform for outreach and interaction [7,8].

Over the past few years, orthodontics has witnessed, notable progress, specifically in the application of Temporary Anchorage Devices (TADs). The use of TADs has profoundly increased in contemporary orthodontics as this small tool aids in reinforcement of anchorage [9]. The various uses of TADs include overbite correction, space closure, correcting cants of the occlusal plane, uprighting teeth, mesializing, or distalizing molars, intruding teeth and midline correction. Borderline surgical cases where sagittal, vertical and transverse corrections are required can now be corrected non-surgically with the usage of TADs [10,11,12]. Due to their efficacy and adaptability, TADs have attracted considerable interest among the orthodontists, who are keen to delve into and exchange their insights regarding these devices.

In parallel, Instagram has become a virtual platform for the practitioners to share their insights, successes, and challenges related to TADs. Individuals worldwide are sharing their experiences on the platform, spanning from initial consultations to the outcomes of post-treatment. The content on Instagram varies from informative posts crafted by the experts to firsthand narratives from patients undergoing orthodontic treatment with TAD assistance [13]. Consequently, Instagram has emerged as a compelling space for analyzing the perspectives, attitudes, and trends surrounding TADs in the realm of orthodontics.

Hence, it appears crucial to assess the completeness of the available information on this potent social media tool. Thus, this study aims to categorize, quantify, and interpret data derived from Instagram posts containing the most commonly used TADS hashtags in their captions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional analysis inductive content analysis was performed and the data was gathered from Instagram (www.instagram.com), focusing on posts related to TADs. Approval from the ethical committee was not required and as the study did not include patients, consent was not required. To pinpoint the most popular hashtags associated with this topic, 'Google Trends' was employed. Each term was input into the search feature by selecting the 'Tags' tab as part of the search strategy. The chosen hashtags for data collection were #tads, #miniscrews, and #miniscrewsinorthodontics. For each hashtag, the total number of posts were gathered and classified them as either photographs or videos. At the initial evaluation stage, the dataset comprised 29,300 posts for #tads, 1,000 posts for #miniscrews, and 1,000 posts for #miniscrewsinorthodontics. The authors only scrutinised posts that were visible on users' accounts and did not consider archived/deleted posts. We did not seek ethics approval/consent from users, as we examined information that was publicly available and non-identifying.

Two researchers collected and utilized ideas or concepts that emerged from reviews of data to shape coding frames. For each Instagram post, we used inductive coding methods to analyze images first, and then we moved on to associated captions and comments. Simple descriptive analysis was also used.

Initially, the posts associated with #miniscrews and #miniscrewsinorthodontics were excluded from the dataset. Furthermore, posts containing Reels (650) and videos (304) were omitted, focusing solely on photographic content. To ensure the latest data, an Instagram filter was applied to retrieve the most 'Recent Posts'. Afterward, a thorough screening process was undertaken, filtering out duplicate posts and those unrelated to orthodontics. This curation resulted in a final dataset comprising 3,348 posts. In a subsequent evaluation, certain posts were deemed non-contributory as they lacked detailed treatment mechanics information or were primarily promotional in nature.

During further reviewing of the posts, some posts presented partial information on biomechanics. Unfortunately, these posts lacked the crucial preoperative and postoperative photographs required for comprehensive analysis. Following a meticulous screening process, a specific subset of 88 posts that perfectly aligned with all the inclusion criteria. This number was considered sufficient based on previous research [14,15]. These 88 posts became the focal point of our in-depth analysis and these posts were analysed based on the different biomechanics. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Flowchart representation of screened and included Instagram posts

Descriptive statistics were performed by entering the extracted data into Microsoft Excel (version 16.0, Microsoft, Redmond, WA, USA). The frequencies and percentages of relevant posts were calculated.

RESULTS

A total of 88 posts were analysed in this study with the highest number of posts attributed to #tads which was further divided based on biomechanics. Through frequency and percentage calculations, it was determined that merely 2.6% of the social media information analyzed was particularized and comprehensive. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Pie diagram showing percentage division of included Instagram posts

Of the total posts screened, Intrusion mechanics yielded the highest average number of post and this category was further divided into divided into incisor intrusion (31.71 %, n= 13), molar intrusion (19.51%, n= 8) and full arch intrusion (24.39% n= 10) followed by Cant correction (n= 17).

A total of 14 posts were found for En masse distalization with a higher focus on the maxilla (n=10). Comparatively a smaller number of posts were found for crossbite correction (n=4) and molar uprighting(n=4). The number of posts based on the biomechanics are shown in Table I.

Table 1: Categorization of included Instagram posts

Categorization based on biomechanics	n=88 (%)
INTRUSION	41 (56.59)
Incisor intrusion	13 (31.71)
Molar Intrusion	8 (19.51)
Full Arch Intrusion	10 (24.39)
EN MASSE DISTALISATION	14 (15.91)
Maxilla	10 (71.43)
Mandible	4 (28.57)
EN MASSE SPACE CLOSURE	8 (9.1)
CANT CORRECTION	17 (19.32)
MISCELLANEOUS MECHANICS	18 (20.45)
Crossbite correction	4 (22.22)
Indirect anchorage	10 (55.56)
Molar uprighting	4 (22.22)

DISCUSSION

Instagram offers a distinct advantage over other social media platforms due to its emphasis on visual content, making information gathering more user-friendly [16]. This visual-centric approach is particularly valuable in the field of orthodontics as the branch is closely associated with smile and facial esthetics. Consequently, Instagram has become the go-to platform for patients seeking insights into their health concerns. Recent statistics reveal that over one billion users engage with Instagram each month, sharing in excess of 100 million posts. In the realm of orthodontics, patients find it quick and convenient to access posts pertaining to treatments and often share their own treatment journeys and experiences. Instagram's unique position in the social media landscape is further underscored by the ease of accessing and the effectiveness of information collection through shared videos and images [15].

It is a fact that patient experience regarding healthcare services has improved in the presence of social media and ample literature supports this evidence [17,18]. The traditional treatment modalities has now been replaced by TADs reinforced anchorage which has enabled orthodontic clinicians to accomplish profound clinical solutions. Therefore, the present study aimed to investigate the influence of social media on orthodontic-related posts shared on Instagram.

On social media platforms, it is evident that posts focusing on orthodontic treatment biomechanics, particularly those associated with esthetic corrections, were more prevalent. Clinicians who share these posts not only aim to disseminate valuable biomechanical insights but also harbor an interest in building their own popularity. The visual appeal of a post plays a pivotal role in its memorability, and clinicians are well aware of this fact. Consequently, it is reasonable to consider that remarkable visual influence on patients may have prompted clinicians to utilize the platform as a medium for advertising their orthodontic expertise and services.

Instagram, like other platforms has hashtag(#) feature which when applied shows us the 'top' or most popular posts first and then the other related posts are arranged in a chronological order. Thus, in the present study #tads, #miniscrews and #miniscrewsinorthodontics were analysed. #miniscrews and #miniscrewsinorthodontics were excluded due to their relatively lower numbers and as they imbricated #tads.

By applying the "recent posts" filter on Instagram, it became evident that the majority of posts included photos showcased Cant correction. This may be attributed to the visual appeal of smile correction, which tends to attract viewers. Additionally, a slightly higher number of posts featuring full arch intrusion, incisor intrusion, and maxillary en masse distalization were found, as these biomechanics also contribute to smile correction.

In contrast, posts related to molar intrusion, en masse space closure, mandibular en masse distalization, molar uprighting, crossbite correction, and indirect anchorage were comparatively less common in the dataset. The results were surprising because apart from cant correction the most common use of TADs was space closure but it attributed to about only 8% of total posts.

The trajectory of popular social media platforms like Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook suggests that their prominence is likely to persist and even grow in the coming years [19]. These online social networks may well evolve into potent supplements to traditional sources of health information [17]. As the influence of social media continues to surge within the field of clinical orthodontics, it becomes increasingly essential for researchers to acquaint themselves with qualitative research techniques that can effectively analyze the content present on these platforms.

A study was conducted to check the accuracy and type of Instagram posts related to the most commonly marketed orthodontics products. Among all the posts only 2.6% were found 'objectively true' [20]. Thus any marketed product on social media platform should be verified for the accuracy of information

before promoting it. A previous study by Knosel and Jung for assessment of informational content on YouTube related to orthodontics found that most of the videos were shared by patients undergoing orthodontic treatment. They further concluded that the videos shared by orthodontists were inadequate in content and most of the videos were for advertising purpose [21].

Thus, it is the social responsibility of the healthcare professionals to check for the completeness of the information shared.

Future research endeavours should consider extended timeframes to encompass a wider spectrum of distinctive themes. Additionally, exploring other social media platforms beyond the current focus could yield valuable insights, as the landscape of social media is dynamic and constantly evolving.

CONCLUSION

- The Instagram platform is a great tool for information sharing.
- Only 2.6% of recently available information pertaining to TADs is complete.
- Thus, health care providers should be careful before sharing information on an open platform so the population is not misled.

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